

The Appeal of Islam Among African Americans:

A Missiological and Historical Evaluation of Christian-Muslim Engagement in Urban Contexts

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The horrors of the Holocaust during World War II, along with the continued rhetoric of radical Zionists who defended slavery and participated in American racism, contributed to the strength and appeal of the Nation of Islam (NOI). For many African Americans, the same Jews who presented themselves as victims were seen as active oppressors—tainting the legacy of the prophets, crucifying Christ (a dark-skinned man), and upholding economic systems that exploited Black communities.¹ This perception, combined with the oppressive realities of urban life—where Jewish-owned businesses were often seen as contributors to Black economic struggle—fueled the NOI’s anti-Semitic and anti-Christian sentiment. What the Nation offered, however, was not just condemnation but an alternative religious identity that promised dignity and belonging to those fed up with the contradictions of a white man’s Christianity.

Under Elijah Muhammad’s leadership, the NOI attracted thousands of African American men during the Civil Rights and Black Power movements. His followers, known as the Fruit of Islam (FOI), rejected both integrationist protest and revolutionary militancy. Instead, they pursued justice through racial separation, spiritual discipline, and economic self-reliance. In return, the NOI gave them manhood, purpose, and a sense of divine calling—fostering a deep appreciation for Islam as it was taught within their community.²

Although the Nation of Islam diverges significantly from traditional Islamic orthodoxy, its widespread appeal reveals a deeper rejection of Christianity. This rejection has increased the embrace of Islam in urban Black communities, not because of theological alignment, but because of the dignity, self-definition, and historical consciousness it offers. Over time, many drawn to the NOI have transitioned into Sunni orthodoxy—underscoring how identity-based religion often paves the way for theological commitment. Much like in America’s colonial era, when “Christian” came to represent whiteness rather than sincere faith, the racialization of religion continues to shape how Black Americans respond to both Christianity and Islam.³

While mainstream Islamic theology offers a coherent and disciplined religious system, its appeal to African Americans in urban contexts—especially through sects like the Nation of Islam and the Five Percent Nation—is often rooted in its affirmation of Black dignity, self-determination, and critique of Christianity’s role in white supremacy. This paper argues that Christian witness in urban contexts must engage with the historical failures of the Church while articulating a gospel that restores both identity and justice. To support this argument, the discussion will first explore the appeal of Islam in African American urban communities, then examine how mainstream Islamic theology interacts with that experience, assess the Church’s historical failure to affirm Black dignity, and ultimately propose a reimagined Christian witness rooted in restoration, justice, and identity.

The dissemination and implementation of Islam within the African American community is both complex and layered. While Islam’s presence in Black America can be traced back to enslaved Africans from Muslim-majority regions, the more visible growth of Islam in the

¹ Stephen H. Norwood and Eunice G. Pollack, “White Devils, Satanic Jews: The Nation of Islam from Fard to Farrakhan,” *Modern Judaism: A Journal of Jewish Ideas & Experience* 40, no. 2 (2020): 137–68, <https://doi.org/10.1093/mj/kjaa006>.

² Dawn-Marie Gibson, “Making Original Men: Elijah Muhammad, The Nation of Islam, and The Fruit of Islam,” *The Journal of Religious History* 44, no. 3 (2020): 319–37, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9809.12684>.

³ Algernon Austin, “Rethinking Race and the Nation of Islam, 1930–1975,” *Ethnic & Racial Studies* 26, no. 1 (2003): 52, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870022000025270>.

twentieth century is often linked to the charisma and influence of leaders like Noble Drew Ali, Prince D. Solomon, and Elijah Muhammad. These men blended elements of Christian theology, Black empowerment, Islamic culture, and even Hebrew ideas to craft religious messages that resonated deeply with African Americans. Their messages capitalized on shared pain—anger toward white oppression, the failures of Christianity, and a longing for reclaimed heritage. They didn't need theological precision; they needed emotional and cultural relevance.⁴

Leaders like Elijah Muhammad presented a radical reimagining of humanity's origins—declaring that the original man was Black, that Allah Himself was “the Supreme Black Man,” and that the white race had been created for the purpose of destroying the Black nation. While these ideas are heretical to Sunni Islam, they were powerful to a generation of African Americans who were tired of being told that their suffering was theologically irrelevant. The church's silence—or worse, complicity—in slavery and segregation had created a theological vacuum, and the Nation of Islam filled it. As Carl Ellis notes, Black churches had begun avoiding themes of empowerment, dignity, and divine identity—retreating into a theology of suffering that no longer spoke to African Americans yearning for significance.⁵

Today, the number of Sunni African American Muslims far outweighs those in Black nationalist groups, yet these groups still serve as powerful gateways. A striking example of this is seen in the American prison system—where the largest percentage of Black male converts to Islam are found. Incarcerated Black men, disillusioned with the perceived weakness of Christianity and its association with white, feminized, and passive expressions of faith, often find Islam to be an empowering alternative. Islam's discipline, structure, and sense of global brotherhood appeal to men who feel abandoned and disoriented. While many begin with the Nation of Islam or Five Percent Nation, over time, they often transition into Sunni orthodoxy. As of the year 2000, nearly a third of the estimated six million Muslims in America were converts—and 85 to 90 percent of those were African Americans. A major percentage of these conversions originated in prisons.⁶

For many, conversion to Islam is not primarily theological—it's personal, cultural, and restorative. The church, especially in urban contexts, is often seen not only as disconnected from Black struggle but as reinforcing individual blame rather than challenging systemic injustice. Even some middle-class Black churches have communicated that those suffering simply need to try harder, ignoring the structural barriers that create and sustain poverty and incarceration. In contrast, Black Muslim communities have addressed themes of dignity, identity, and divine significance head-on—particularly among men. They offer a system that opposes feminine leadership, emphasizes male strength, and casts religion as a call to order rather than emotion. This makes Islam attractive to Black men seeking strength, clarity, and a cultural home.

⁴ Patrick D. Bowen, “Prince D. Solomon and the Birth of African-American Islam,” *Journal of Theta Alpha Kappa* 38, no. 1 (2014): 1–19, <https://research-ebSCO-com.i.ezproxy.nypl.org/linkprocessor/plink?id=0bc6796d-8f6e-3231-8ae2-57e4e6ffd93a>.

⁵ Edward Gilbreath, “How Islam Is Winning Black America,” interview with Carl Ellis, *Christianity Today*, April 3, 2000.

⁶ David J. Feddes, “Islam among African-American Prisoners,” *Missiology* 36, no. 4 (2008): 505–21, <https://research-ebSCO-com.i.ezproxy.nypl.org/linkprocessor/plink?id=9236a58c-4771-3702-813a-4171c93a088a>.

The emotional rejection of Christianity by many African Americans, especially men, stems not from a hatred of Jesus but from a perceived betrayal by the Church. Islam offers a version of faith that appears more dignifying and disciplined. As one sociologist observes, “All too often, their conversion reflects a serious inadequacy in their religious environment.” The church’s “fuzzy Christology” and its inability to address the real pain and questions of African American life leave many vulnerable to religious alternatives that speak more clearly to their experience. Black nationalist versions of Islam may not hold theological credibility within mainstream Islamic tradition, but they speak powerfully to systemic oppression and the hunger for dignity.

The Nation of Islam (NOI), though it shares some surface-level continuities with orthodox Islam, contains numerous doctrinal deviations that orthodox Muslims consider heretical. One point of overlap is Islam’s high view of Jesus (as Isa), which the NOI strategically uses to blend Christianity and Judaism into its religious framework—making its message more palatable to African Americans raised in Christian traditions. However, much of the NOI’s appeal lies not in theology but in its sharp critique of Christianity, which it portrays as complicit in the oppression of Black people. The NOI positions the church as part of the problem—not the solution—to Black suffering.

A key theological departure is the NOI’s elevation of Wallace Fard as “Allah in person” and Elijah Muhammad as his final prophet. This directly contradicts the core Islamic belief that Muhammad ibn Abdullah is the last prophet. Fard, who was active in Detroit in the 1930s, presented himself as a messianic figure revealing to African Americans hidden truths about their stolen African heritage. He taught dietary discipline and denounced American cuisine as a tool of white oppression. His message, grounded in so-called “scientific religiosity,” framed Islam as a method for achieving physical health, economic strength, and community dignity.⁷

The NOI also advanced a racially charged doctrine in which white people were depicted as devils, biologically engineered by the evil scientist Yakub to destroy the Black race. While absurd to mainstream Islamic theology, this myth tapped into the very real trauma of white supremacy and slavery. Elijah Muhammad formalized the divinity of Fard and taught that Fard would return in glory to destroy America and punish white oppressors. For the NOI, salvation was not spiritual in the traditional sense but physical—achieved through longevity, prosperity, and freedom from white systems. Their dietary teachings were part of a holistic program for self-reliance and liberation, viewed as sacred acts of resistance.⁸

The NOI also rejected a transcendent deity and the universal implications of orthodox Islam. It embraced a racially exclusive message, minimizing the global, multi-ethnic, and proselytizing nature of Islam. It opposed mainstream Islamic teachings such as bodily resurrection, the existence of an immaterial soul, and the centrality of Hadith literature—essential in Sunni jurisprudence. Even their practice of fasting diverged: the NOI rejected Ramadan and instead promoted fasting during December to symbolically oppose Christian holidays and Western customs. Their reinterpretations of Islamic teachings served a

⁷ Nils Duranton, “Life in Abundance: Diet, Black Health and Spirituality in the Nation of Islam, 1930–1975,” *Studies in Religion* 53, no. 4 (2024): 593–611, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00084298241238138>.

⁸ Dawn-Marie Gibson, “Making Original Men: Elijah Muhammad, The Nation of Islam, and The Fruit of Islam,” *The Journal of Religious History* 44, no. 3 (2020): 319–37, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9809.12684>.

broader purpose: creating an empowering Black identity distinct from what they perceived as the colonized version of Christianity.⁹

By contrast, orthodox Islam affirms a transcendent God, rooted in the declaration of faith (Shahada): "There is no god but Allah, and Muhammad is his messenger." This declaration alone disqualifies Elijah Muhammad as a prophet. Orthodox Islam is structured around the Five Pillars—Shahada (faith), Salah (prayer), Zakat (charity), Sawm (fasting), and Hajj (pilgrimage)—and relies on the Qur'an and Hadith as divine and authoritative. The Qur'an, revealed in Arabic, is considered God's literal word, and even translations are viewed as interpretations rather than true scripture.¹⁰

While orthodox Islam rejects racial superiority, it does contain critiques of Christianity that African Americans may resonate with, such as the idea that Christians corrupted the original message of Jesus. However, its appeal to many African Americans has more to do with dignity and discipline than with doctrine. Sunni Islam offers clarity, global unity, and cultural strength. However, the initial draw often begins with the Black-centered theology of movements like the Nation of Islam, which confront white supremacy directly and offer a path to reclaim identity and self-worth.¹¹

It is no surprise that Western Christianity in America has often been viewed with suspicion in the Black community due to its long-standing complicity in slavery, segregation, and even its theological defense of white supremacy. Christians in the antebellum South didn't merely tolerate slavery—they baptized it. Southern white Christians affirmed that God sanctioned slavery in Scripture and that bondage under white authority was the natural state for people of African descent. Acceptance of race-based chattel slavery became, in many places, a requirement for biblical orthodoxy. Entire denominations split over the issue—Methodists, Baptists, and Presbyterians—and the formation of the Southern Baptist Convention was rooted entirely in its defense of slavery.¹²

Even those who opposed slavery often upheld anti-Black racism. Abraham Lincoln, though heralded as the "Great Emancipator," once declared he was not in favor of the social or political equality of Black people. He even proposed colonization plans to send formerly enslaved people to Liberia or Haiti rather than grant them full participation in American life. The issue was deeply moral and spiritual. South Carolina leaders openly stated that northern states had "denounced as sinful the institution of slavery." Many Christians were willing to die to defend it.¹³

The Bible itself was weaponized. "Slave Bibles" were published, omitting entire books and passages that could incite hope or rebellion—like the Exodus story—while leaving in verses like Ephesians 6:5, "Slaves, obey your earthly masters." This deliberate censorship betrayed the liberating heart of the gospel.¹⁴

⁹ Duranton, "Life in Abundance," 600.

¹⁰ Daniel Brown, *A New Introduction to Islam*, 3rd ed. (Hoboken, NJ: Wiley-Blackwell, 2017), 197.

¹¹ Gibson, "Making Original Men," 325.

¹² Jemar Tisby, *The Color of Compromise: The Truth about the American Church's Complicity in Racism* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2019), Kindle edition.

¹³ Tisby, *The Color of Compromise*, Kindle edition.

¹⁴ Michel Martin, "Slave Bible From the 1800s Omitted Key Passages That Could Incite Rebellion," *NPR*, December 9, 2018,

The betrayal continued into the 20th century, as many evangelical Christians remained silent—or outright resistant—during the Civil Rights Movement. Their silence often aimed to preserve classism, protect white political power, and maintain cultural control. Meanwhile, dominant Christian imagery reinforced whiteness: a blonde-haired, blue-eyed Jesus popularized by Warner Sallman’s Head of Christ hung in homes, churches, and Sunday school classrooms. Art historian Anna Swartwood House reminds us that these depictions were based not on history but on Renaissance art and European ideals—a long tradition of white Christians making Christ in their own image.¹⁵

This cultural dominance extended to theology and worship. White theological voices have been elevated as standard, while the Black church’s contributions are dismissed as emotional or theologically weak. In many seminaries, less affluent or nonwhite churches are portrayed as problematic or deficient. Even today, white churches often fail to meaningfully platform Black theologians or grant them real power to influence dominant narratives. This theological gatekeeping reinforces a Christianity that is more European in expression than reflective of its African and Middle Eastern origins.¹⁶

As Henry McNeal Turner, AME bishop, and Black liberation theologian, once said, “Every race of people... have conveyed the idea that the God who made them... was symbolized by themselves, and why should not the Negro believe that he resembles God as much as other people?” Yet, white supremacy in the church continues to shape which voices, images, and practices are seen as “normal” and which are considered “other.”¹⁷

Even music reflects this imbalance. Gospel music—rooted in Black culture—is often relegated to Black spaces, while Contemporary Christian Music (CCM), targeting white audiences, is labeled simply as “Christian.” This naming reflects a broader privileging of white Protestant norms. Scholars argue that for Black communities, religious identity is tied to racial identity and historical oppression. Music, worship style, and theology serve spiritual purposes and as tools of resistance, cultural continuity, and meaning-making.¹⁸

Sadly, racism remains a marginal issue in much of U.S. theology—even within liberationist circles. Black and womanist theologies continue to be sidelined in Catholic and Protestant institutions alike. For the American church to recover its witness, it must stop ignoring this history and begin to reckon with its deep entanglement in systems of racial oppression. The failure to address Black dignity is not just a historical oversight but a theological crisis.

Perhaps a more accurate understanding of our Christian faith—particularly the incarnation—offers a compelling framework for gospel witness in urban Black Muslim contexts.

<https://www.npr.org/2018/12/09/674995075/slave-bible-from-the-1800s-omitted-key-passages-that-could-ignite-rebellion>.

¹⁵ W. Gabriel Selassie I, “White Jesus Must Die: Decoding Black Jesus—The Iconography of Coon Christ and Jesus of the People,” *Delos: A Journal of Translation and World Literature* 37, no. 1 (2022): 15+, accessed April 9, 2025, <http://dx.doi.org.i.ezproxy.nypl.org/10.5744/delos.2022.1002>.

¹⁶ Mary Doak, “Cornel West’s Challenge to the Catholic Evasion of Black Theology,” *Theological Studies* 63, no. 1 (2002): 87–106, <https://research-ebSCO-com.i.ezproxy.nypl.org/linkprocessor/plink?id=c51889a2-26a6-3354-a6e9-d396c8d877af>.

¹⁷ Selassie, “White Jesus Must Die,” 15+.

¹⁸ Omotayo O. Banjo and Kesha Morant Williams, “Behind the Music: Exploring Audiences’ Attitudes toward Gospel and Contemporary Christian Music,” *Journal of Communication & Religion* 37, no. 3 (2014): 117–38, <https://doi.org/10.5840/jcr201437323>.

By its very nature, the Christian faith affirms the dignity of the human body, including the Black body. The doctrine of the incarnation means that God entered human history through a specific people in a specific place. The Jewish Jesus, born under imperial oppression, was not a myth or a ghost, nor a demigod detached from real struggle. "He was flesh and blood, like all of us—and he belonged to a particular people." That particularity matters.¹⁹

Science confirms that Jesus's earthly body—living in first-century Palestine—looked nothing like the whitewashed portrayals made popular in Western Christianity. Yet if we respond by simply preaching a Black Jesus in skin tone, we risk perpetuating the very problem we seek to fix. Centering race as the primary draw into Christianity can lead people to the idol of their own self-image rather than the surpassing greatness of Christ himself. The gospel is not a celebration of our likeness to God but a revelation of God's holiness in contrast to our sin. The beauty of the incarnation is not just that God looks like us, but that God came to dwell with us. Still, the incarnation is more than a theological abstraction. It affirms embodied existence. "If the incarnation is not a sham," one writer puts it, "then it is also true to say that Jesus... is Black." In other words, if Jesus was truly a Jew who suffered under empire, and if his suffering is what saves us, then he must be seen today in the crucified bodies in our midst. The Blackness of Jesus's Jewishness is racial, historical, social, and theological. As James Cone affirmed, "He is Black because he was a Jew," not in color but in condition. To be Black in America is to share in Christ's social location.²⁰

This gospel is not merely about salvation from sin but restoration and liberation. Jesus healed physical bodies—not to perform tricks, but to show that the body matters to God. "Salvation is the healing of the wounds wrought by estrangement... the transformation of something broken into something whole." That wholeness includes the physical. It includes justice. It includes community. Jesus's ministry was a Spirit-empowered witness to the kind of kingdom where the poor are lifted, the blind see, the oppressed are freed, and the broken are restored.²¹

This is why the Black church is critical in bridging theology and identity. That Black Americans still hold to Christianity—a religion historically used to enslave and dehumanize them—is a miracle of grace. Their faith stands as a living testimony to the resurrection. "Who knows suffering better than the Black church?" one theologian asks. "Who has shown the world what it means to imitate Jesus?" As James Cone powerfully observed, it was Black Christians who truly believed the gospel that white Christians used to oppress them—because they knew, without doubt, that Christ had been unjustly hung on a tree. His suffering mirrored theirs. His story was their story. And it was this shared reality that made the gospel not only believable but deeply true. Their example of Christlike love, nonviolent protest, and radical forgiveness is one of the clearest demonstrations of true Christianity America has ever seen.²²

¹⁹ Brad East, "Jewish Jesus, Black Christ," *Christian Century* 139, no. 3 (2022): 20–25, <https://research-ebSCO-com.i.ezproxy.nypl.org/linkprocessor/plink?id=92928436-8756-3e65-bc93-f83608d66f94>.

²⁰ East, "Jewish Jesus, Black Christ," 23.

²¹ Ted Peters, "Wholeness in Salvation and Healing," *Lutheran Quarterly* 5, no. 3 (1991): 297–314, <https://research-ebSCO-com.i.ezproxy.nypl.org/linkprocessor/plink?id=c3e8d235-38f4-3af6-a62f-8005c7c0423f>.

²² East, "Jewish Jesus, Black Christ," 23.

This same Black church is positioned to offer a faithful witness to Black Muslims. It is a witness not rooted in guilt or argument, but in embodied identity, power, and grace. It is also a charismatic witness—one that embraces the power of the Holy Spirit, the prophetic voice, and the miraculous. In this way, Christianity has the capacity to meet Muslims on spiritual grounds, affirming the presence of divine power while introducing them to the living Christ. Unlike fragile identities built on performance—prayer, fasting, and external discipline—Christian identity offers permanence. It is not earned but received. Jesus gave identity to those who had none. He called fishermen and tax collectors to be kingdom leaders. He promised them, not just transformation but permanence: "a royal priesthood," "a holy nation," "a city on a hill." And He continues to do the same today.

Our examination brings us to a clear conclusion: Christianity does not lack a message that offers dignity and identity to Black people. The issue is that the Church has often failed to demonstrate that Jesus actually provides these things. Islam's appeal among African Americans—especially in urban communities—is not rooted in superior truth but in its ability to offer answers to questions the people are actually asking. It speaks directly to questions of justice, purpose, and power.

The Christian church has failed to answer these questions—not because it can't, but because it hasn't. Christianity holds the truth, but no one wants to hear it when it comes from a Church that won't confront its own sins. Until the Church names these failures honestly, its witness will remain compromised.

If we want to see people in Harlem turn to Christ, our message must be Christ-centered, robust in its Christology, and unapologetically contextualized to the wounds and hopes of this community. People are longing for a God who sees them, dignifies them, and gives them purpose. We must show that Jesus is that God—not just in words, but in the way we live, preach, and love.

If we truly know this Jesus—this healer, liberator, and restorer—we must declare him boldly. Only Jesus can restore what oppression has stolen. Only Jesus can offer an identity that suffering cannot erase. And only Jesus can turn pain into power and give us a name that no system, structure, or oppressor can take away.

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